

INNOVATION THE CLUSTER APPROACH ON THE BASIS OF IMPROVEMENT OF PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF FUTURE TEACHERS

Shamshodjon Boltayev

Teacher of the department of methods of physical culture

Chirchik state pedagogical university

E-mail: shamshodjonboltayev96@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article outlines the inter-clonal sectors interaction school of pedagogical experience as a laboratory for the innovative cluster approach by increasing the basi. Also, physical culture and development of an innovative cluster is not the only format aimed at the teaching of the educational direction of the school between tea and munching aimed at increasing general second increasing visionary, but also at developing the scientific and creative potential of students and the professional personnel from the point of view of region's students need for the future.

Key words. Innovative educational cluster in teaching, school-laboratory professional, innovative activity, inter-industry cooperation, region, model, educational direction of physical culture, experience, and competence.

INTRODUCTION

Sh.M.Since the first days of his presidency, Mirziyoyev has been paying serious attention to the issues of training innovative and creatively thinking modern personnel in our country, educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, as owners of high morale, improving the educational system for this purpose. Consistent measures are being implemented in our country to raise the educational system to a new level, improve the quality of pedagogical training on the basis of Advanced International Standards and increase the level of coverage with higher pedagogical education.

In education, an educator is distinguished by his creativity, activity, individuality, critical thinking, professional pedagogical competence, that is, by a set of competencies and the desire to constantly develop and develop the level of pedagogical skill through the introduction of innovative educational technologies.

To acquire professional skills, pedagogical orientation, professionally significant personal qualities, basic pedagogical abilities, professional competence, continuous self-improvement, professional development, pedagogical creativity and innovation are necessary.

Cluster policy serves as the basis of a regional economic development strategy, and in relation to the educational system, the cluster can be referred to as an innovation center that synthesizes professional forces to address the issue of training taking into account the needs of the region.

Education is a complex system in which there are many independent complementary and interdependent parts. Any system works effectively only if there is feedback. Therefore, the school and institute must learn to develop forms of cooperation. To carry out such cooperation, it is advisable to use the cluster model in organizing the educational process.

Pedagogical education innovation cluster is a group of geographically localized organizations that cooperate on the basis of contracts and participate in the implementation of scientific, educational and innovative goals for the training of educational specialists.

As the most basic condition and form of implementation of the innovative cluster of pedagogical education, innovative experimental sites "School-laboratory" can be obtained. The innovative cluster of pedagogical education is a strategic research direction of the educational direction ChDPU "Physical Culture", and the "school-laboratory" is its core – a form of implementation in practice. "School-laboratories" perform important tasks related to the creation and experimental testing of scientific and pedagogical innovative projects.

Today, 4 such "school-laboratory" innovative experimental sites have been established in general secondary education schools in Chirchik, Tashkent region. In order to carry out the work on this subject on a systematic and specific plan, cooperation agreements and a plan of measures were developed between the 24-25 general secondary education schools of the Department of public education of the city of Chirchik and the direction of Education "Physical Culture". The purpose of the innovative experimental sites "school-laboratory" is to develop scientific, methodological and educational tools between the types of education in the process of continuing education, to experiment and test scientific and pedagogical projects related to the practical implementation of the innovative cluster of pedagogical education.

SUMMARY

Pedagogical education it is important to implement an innovative cluster as a physical culture educational direction and a means of cooperating schools. The organization of an innovative cluster of pedagogical education provides a solution to the most important task of modern teacher professional training – the transition of specialists from reproductive production to their individual and creative training, as well as the formation of a creative competitive personality of the teacher.

REFERENCES:

1. Mukhamedov G'.I., Khodjamqulov U.N. Innovative cluster of pedagogical education: definition, description, classification. Chirchiq, University-2019.
2. Khojamqulov U.N. School-laboratory. Chirchiq-2019.
3. T.Achilov. Pedagogical education didactic possibilities of interaction in an innovative cluster approach. Public education. No. 5. T. 2021.
4. Boltayev Sh.E. Abdurahmanov Sh. Kuziyeva F.B. Improving the effectiveness of physical education classes by using the cluster method in secondary school students. Academic Research in Educational Sciences VOLUME 3 ISSUE 12 2022. Pp. 339-342.